

**FORMATION OF STUDENTS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION IN THE
BASICS OF THE MATHEMATICS COURSE, SKILLS AND ABILITIES
NECESSARY FOR DEEPER ASSIMILATION OF THE MATHEMATICS
COURSE**

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Methodology of teaching mathematics,
theory of elementary mathematics course
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Annotation: This article covers information about formation of students of primary education in the basics of the mathematics course, skills and abilities necessary for deeper assimilation of the mathematics course. On the other hand, basic methods that can be utilize in teaching mathematics at the primary schools and their importance in organizing effective lessons.

Key words: *primary grades, mathematics curriculum, general principles, differential approach, emotional-volitional spheres, full-value acquisition, abstraction, clarification.*

The teaching of mathematics in primary grades is generally considered as the first step in mastering the school mathematics course. Therefore, when working in primary classes, it is necessary to take into account the general issues involved in teaching mathematics in secondary schools and correctly assess the importance of primary education in solving these issues. Mathematics is important in two ways, because:

1. it contains important skills and knowledge for participating in society as an adult, and
2. it serves as a gatekeeper for all sorts of opportunities in study and employment.

Young people need mathematics in order to live better lives. Primary school

mathematics is the foundation of all later mathematics learning, again in two ways:

- the concepts of early mathematics are the roots of later ideas, and
- young people's belief in their ability to do mathematics and their willingness to engage with mathematics are shaped by their primary school mathematics learning experiences.

Many of the issues in the secondary mathematics curriculum must be mastered in the primary grades to such an extent that they remain in the minds of students throughout their lives, while other issues need to be studied in detail in the early stages of instruction in later grades. entered only for the purpose of preparation for exit; or introduced to have the opportunity to increase the level of thinking ability in the process of formation of some skills and abilities[1].

The knowledge, studies and the above-mentioned considerations should be taken into account when it comes to the conscious and sustained acquisition of a certain amount of skills. The mathematics course involves summarizing educational materials to the extent that students can, explaining the general principles and laws underlying the studied mathematical facts, and explaining the connections between the observed phenomena. This mainly refers to the study of the properties of actions, existing connections based on them , mathematical relationships and connections that are the basis of practical learning and skills that are formed in children.

The need for an initial mathematical individual and differential approach to children depends on their psychophysical development in the formation of concepts, against the background of organic or functional pathology, in which the disorders appear in different forms. As a rule, they are accompanied by disorders of the central nervous system, high nervous activity, and manifest themselves in a variety of cognitive problems — permanent or temporary, with varying degrees of severity. For intellectually retarded students, the study of mathematical material

poses great difficulties, the reasons for which are primarily explained by the peculiarities of the development of the cognitive and emotional-volitional spheres of mentally retarded school students. According to research conducted by experts in the field of characteristics of mentally retarded children, you should pay attention to the following characteristics that are characteristic of them:

- with the underdevelopment of all neuropsychic functions, mainly the permanent dysfunction of abstract forms of thinking;
- combination of intellectual disability with arbitrary forms and imbalances of speech, perception, memory, attention and behavior;
- The slow pace of thinking and the inactivity of mental processes determine the inability to adapt the learned method of action in the learning process to new conditions;
- Lack of development of thinking affects all mental processes: cognition, memory, attention.

First of all, all the functions of distraction and generalization suffer, the components of mental activity associated with the analytical-synthetic activity of the brain are disrupted. In the emotional-volitional sphere, this is manifested in the lack of development of complex emotions and arbitrary forms of behavior. Although the teaching of mathematics is practical and interrelated with labor education, painting, science, geography, history, and physical education, students with intellectual disabilities must master the existing set of theoretical concepts.

Teaching students to use acquired knowledge, training and skills in different conditions can be considered as a special issue of students. At the same time, the application of knowledge is one of the important means of increasing the effectiveness of children's educational work. Psychologists have proven that full-value acquisition of knowledge and educational skills can be achieved only as a result of their independent application in variable conditions. It is precisely on this basis that it can be eliminated to a large extent, which will necessarily arise when

children move from elementary grades to the next grade in school, and vice versa, if the teacher does not pay special attention to comprehensive knowledge and exposes children to the same type of questions, tasks, expressions, problems, this increases the complexity of the transition to science teaching in the 5th grade. This issue is inextricably linked with the more general issue of developing children's cognitive abilities. A lot of work should be done to observe and compare, distinguish similarities and differences in the phenomena being compared, analysis, synthesis and generalization, abstraction, clarification. The issue of forming students' ability to think mathematically is inextricably linked with the issue of developing correct, clear, short mathematical speech in them. One of the main tasks of teaching mathematics is to provide students with a clear system of calculation, measurement and graphic skills, in other words, this system consists of performing the simplest operations, which has been brought to automaticity due to repeated repetitions[2].

How we teach mathematics in primary schools matters a lot. Every day, primary school teachers have to choose what mathematics they will teach, and how they will teach it. Each choice is significant, shaping what mathematics students will engage with, how students will approach mathematics, and the feelings that students develop about themselves and mathematics. All these factors make planning for, enacting and evaluating mathematics teaching and learning time-consuming and challenging for teachers. Historically, and in other jurisdictions and levels of schooling, this problem has been addressed by trying to provide a comprehensive resource for teachers, such as a textbook or step-by-step handbook, that 'teacherproofs' the decision-making process by telling teachers what to do every step of the way. This often has the effect of 'learnerproofing' the curriculum too, with the pace of teaching being the same for everyone, and teachers 'delivering' what is needed in order to complete activities, with little participation from students. A contrasting approach is when teachers are

positioned as adaptive experts whose job is to make evidence-informed choices about what students need, and then provide for them in a way that makes the students interact deeply with mathematical ideas. Teaching this way may be worthwhile, but it is not quick and easy – and it contains many challenges for primary school teachers[3]. Teachers faced with these challenges are often seeking a magic bullet solution: a book, internet resource, curriculum or method that can support their choices and simplify the task of preparing mathematics lessons every day of the school year. As part of the (very reasonable) quest for manageability, the complexities of both mathematics and students can be sidelined.

Mathematics education starts at the preschool and ends at the university. The methodology of teaching mathematics develops on the basis of the thematic psychological constitution of teaching and general pedagogical theory, as well as the technology of using psychological and pedagogical theory in the teaching of primary mathematics. In addition, in the methodology of teaching mathematics, the teaching methods of mathematics are characterized. In order to open the subject of methods of teaching mathematics, it is necessary to define "the content of teaching mathematics, the main components of the process of teaching mathematics." Teaching elementary school, especially math, is a complex process that controls students' thinking skills using a variety of visual aids[4]. Taking into account the knowledge of students' thinking skills, all this information is processed and transmitted to the student. The student receives information from the teacher, textbooks, other sources, and transmits the acquired knowledge to the teacher. Therefore, in the process of teaching, information is carried out in two directions, that is, this direction is transmitted from the teacher to the learner (direct connection) and from the learner to the teacher (feedback).

In conclusion, it should be noted that The methodology of teaching mathematics depends on the methodology of general mathematics. The laws

defined by the general mathematics methodology are used by the primary mathematics teaching methodology, taking into account the age characteristics of young swimmers. The methodology of teaching primary mathematics is inextricably linked with the science of pedagogy and is based on its laws. There is a two-way connection between the methodology of teaching mathematics and pedagogy. On the one hand, the methodology of mathematics is based on the general theory of pedagogy and is formed on this basis, which ensures the integrity of the methodological and theoretical convergence in solving problems of teaching mathematics. From the second tone, pedagogy relies on the information obtained by special methodologies in the formation of general laws, which ensures its vitality and accuracy. It is based on the thematic material of pedagogical methods, which is used in generalization, and in turn it serves as a guide in the development of methods. Mathematical methodology is related to pedagogical psychology and youth psychology. In solving many problems of upbringing and education it is necessary to use a lot of knowledge about pedagogical psychology and youth psychology.

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